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Sommaire

Éditorial.....	3
<i>Carlos IAFELICE</i> , An analytical approach to the organisation of tonal space in Gherardello's madrigals.....	5
<i>Nicolas MEEÛS</i> , Qu'est-ce qu'un savart ?.....	35
<i>Nicolas BONICHOT</i> , Le contrôle du temps musical à court et moyen terme dans l'oeuvre de Ligeti : l'exemple de <i>Continuum</i> pour clavecin	51
Résumés, Abstracts	71
Bulletin d'abonnement	75

An analytical approach to the organisation of tonal space in Gherardello's madrigals

Carlos C. IAFELICE*

Segmentation is a fundamental procedure for any textual analysis, whether literary¹ or musical². However, the analytical approach to a sung text involves a unique situation, confronted with a confluence of different dialogical discourses at phonetic and phonological levels³. Besides the difference in the comprehensibility of their elements, aspects of the phenomenological coherence between the systems can be very closely located, since both are subjected to time and to the accumulation of facts.

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¹ Dante emphasised the importance of defining the stanzas in order to understand the canzone itself: "Nam ex diffinitionum cognitione diffiniti resultat cognitio" (Dante ALIGHIERI, *De vulgari eloquentia*, Mirko TAVONI (ed.), Milano, Mondadori, 2017, II, IX, 1, p. 358); English translation: "for the understanding of a thing that requires definition flows from familiarity with the elements that compose it" (Steven Botterill (ed. and transl.), Berkeley, Cambridge University Press, 1996, p. 73).

² A process of such importance merges with the discipline of musical analysis itself. Ritva Jonsson and Leo Treitler wrote a passage which we could take as a summary of the confluence between language and melody: "An analogy is drawn between what we can call the constituent-hierarchy of language (phonemes, syllables, words, phrases, sentences or lines, discourses or poems) and that of melody (sounds, neumes, phrases, songs). The movement that is melody can thereby be conceived as a movement from syllable to syllable [...]. The most important analytical strategy for the Latin language is its segmentation into a hierarchy of sense-units called commas, colons, and periods. The composition and analysis of melodies follows the segmentation of language, establishing a phrase hierarchy articulated by the counterparts of the commas, colons, and periods, namely the cadential formulas and the pitch hierarchies of the melody-types and modes" (Ritva JONSSON and Leo TREITLER, "Medieval Music and Language", *Studies in the History of Music*, New York, Broude Brothers, 1983, vol. 1, p. 7).

³ Nicolas RUWET, *Langage, musique, poésie*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1972, pp. 48-49.

In linguistics, for example, the wealth of the subtle and complex semantic relationships in poetry is determined by its final form and not by the direct meaning of its words⁴. This conclusion can easily be transferred to the musical perspective despite the semantic differences. In this case, even if the elements can be isolated and observed as entities *per se*, the connection of the sonic continuum is only established through their projection and movement⁵. We could therefore assume that directionality is an inseparable element of any attempt at textual segmentation.

Moreover, the exploration of tonal space in the secular music of the Italian Ars Nova yields yet another factor: the tradition of modalism as a system. Although this tradition can encourage analysts to situate these pieces in a kind of subordinated tonal organisation, recent conclusions suggest that these compositions are not oriented by a tonal system *per se*⁶, but shaped by an intrinsic tonal structure that supports their musical-poetic nexus. In this case, possible recurrences tend to be understood more as compositional habits than as extracts from an ordered tonal system. Thus, from this perspective, we assume that segmentation and directionality must work together in the task of exploring how the tonal space is organised, without any fixed precepts concerning any modal tradition.

With these assumptions in mind, this article aims to present an analytical method for studying the organisation of tonal space in madrigals, particularly those of Gherardello da Firenze, through the systematic mapping of what we call

⁴ Or by the straight signifier-signified correlation (see *ibid.*, pp. 30-31).

⁵ As already suggested by Johannes de Grocheio when he presents the musical term *tempus*, grounding it in the Aristotelian conception of time (i.e., as "*mensura motus*"): "Est autem tempus, prout hic specialiter accipitur, illud spatium, in quo minima vox vel minimus sonus plenarie profertur seu proferri potest. [...] Ista autem mensura totum cantum mensurat, quemadmodum una revolutio totum tempus" (Johannes DE GROCHEIO, *Ars musicae*, Constant J. Mews *et al.* (ed. and transl.), Kalamazoo, Medieval Institute Publications, 2011, p. 76); English translation: "*Tempus*, as specifically accepted here, is that space in which the smallest voice or the smallest sound is fully articulated or can be articulated. [...] This measure measures all *cantus* just as one rotation [measures] all time" (*Ibid.*, p. 77).

⁶ See Marco MANGANI and Daniele SABAINO, "L'organizzazione dello spazio sonoro nell'opera di Nicolò del Preposto", *Musica e Poesia nel Trecento Italiano*, Antonio CALVIA and Maria Sofia LANUTTI (eds.), Firenze, Edizione del Galluzzo, 2015, p. 283. Yolanda Plumley reached a similar conclusion regarding the French *Ars nova* chanson (Yolanda PLUMLEY, *The Grammar of 14th Century Melody*, New York/London, Garland Publishing, 1996, pp. 5-6).

“caesuras” – in short, transitory interruptions in the sound flow caused either by a pause or by a sustained sonority (resulting from “directed” progressions (i.e., cadences⁷) or even “neutral” ones⁸).

Therefore, the aim of this study is not to provide an exhaustive account of the use of tonal space in Gherardello's madrigals – a task that would not be appropriate for this discussion –, but rather to present elements for proposing an analytical approach to the use of tonal space in these musical works.

The article will be divided into five main parts: the contextual information and general points about Gherardello's madrigals; the presentation of the analytical method; analytical observations; the statistical output of the results; and conclusions.

Gherardello da Firenze and his madrigals

Ser Gherardello da Firenze, one of the first generation of Italian Ars Nova composers, was ordained a priest in 1345 and was a chaplain in Santa Reparata until 1351, when he entered the Vallombrosan Order⁹. It was in this period that “Niccolò figliolo di Francesco” came to be referred to as “Ser Gherardello”. Appointed to be prior in the church of San Remigio in Florence shortly after 1351, he was a frequent guest of the influential circle around the monastery of Santa Trinità between the years 1360 and

⁷ Here the concept is applied specifically as described by Margaret Bent, when she explains her understanding of the term *cadentia* from the medieval perspective. Thus, it is not necessarily a “closure”, but a “dyadic process...[where] some such progressions mark sense-breaks, some mark endings, some may effect a quick change of direction; others cause no discontinuity” (Margaret BENT, *Counterpoint, Composition and Musica Ficta*, New York/London, Routledge, 2002, pp. 13-14).

⁸ These two terms (“directed” and “neutral” progressions) were developed by Sarah Fuller and applied particularly to three- and four-voice works by Machaut (see Sarah FULLER, “Tendencies and Resolutions: Directed Progressions in Ars Nova Music”, *Journal of Music Theory*, 36/2 (1992), pp. 229-258). Here both states are to be understood as two extremes of attenuated parameters regarding harmonic stability, where the sustentation is one of the most distinguishing elements of the caesura's *palette*. It should be noted that the different types of attenuation are the basis for the careful theoretical construction related to the different cadential typologies established by M. Mangani and D. Sabaino in “L'organizzazione dello spazio sonoro nell'opera di Nicolò del Preposto”. However, due to the focus of this investigation on the observation and comparison of “caesuras” in general, the detailed taxonomy set out by M. Mangani and D. Sabaino has not been applied. Also, one can mention other previous important studies that were devoted to French polyphonic music analysis in general, such as: “Voice Function, Sonority, and Contrapuntal Procedure in Late Medieval Polyphony” by Kevin N. Moll (*Current Musicology*, 64 (1998), pp. 26-72), regarding the cadential processes that were applied mainly to the analysis of French Mass settings, and “Theorizing the Cadence in the Music of Machaut” by Jennifer Bain (*Journal of Music Theory*, 47/2 (2003), pp. 325-362), which is devoted to codifying a high number of voice-leading possibilities in cadential progressions in Machaut's secular works.

⁹ See Kurt VON FISCHER and Gianluca D'AGOSTINO, “Gherardello da Firenze”, *Grove Music Online*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2001.

1362, when he also probably met Nicolò del Preposto¹⁰. The date of death, supposedly between 1362-63, is based on the San Remigio records, in which a successor to his position is presented in 1363¹¹. A mention in a sonnet by Simone Peruzzi to Franco Sacchetti¹², which was written around the same year, according to Giuseppe Corsi, also reinforces this assumption¹³.

Gherardello's surviving music is predominantly secular: ten two-voice madrigals¹⁴, five monodic *ballate*, and one three-voice *caccia*¹⁵. Given this circumstance, it is clear that any systematic study of the use of tonal space in his works must be applied to his *ballate* or madrigals. As a first approach to the repertoire, the choice of madrigals was essentially made in relation to the number of voices, which provides a greater amount of information about the use of tonal space than the monodic *ballate*.

Therefore, table 1 presents the madrigals organised alphabetically, as well as the respective musical/poetic sources. As a reference for the modern edition, it was prepared by Alice Colantuoni and the author of this paper as part of the European Ars Nova project¹⁶.

¹⁰ For a detailed presentation of documents relating to Gherardello's presence in Santa Trinità and his connection with Nicolò, see Frank D'ACCONE, "Music and Musicians at the Florentine Monastery of Santa Trinità, 1360-1363", *Quadrivium*, 12 (1971), pp. 131-152, particularly pp. 142-151.

¹¹ See *ibid.*, p. 150.

¹² See Franco SACCHETTI, *Il libro delle rime con le lettere. La battaglia delle belle donne*, Davide PUCCINI (ed.), Torino, Utet, 2007, pp. 175-176.

¹³ Giuseppe CORSI, *Poesie Musicale del Trecento*, Bologna, Commissione per i testi di lingua, 1970, pp. xv-xli. Corsi, based on the Sacchetti-Peruzzi letters, was also convinced that Gherardello's death occurred between 1362 and 1365 (*ibid.*, p. xli).

¹⁴ In the *Rime*, F. Sacchetti indicates that the madrigal "Di bella palla e di valor di petra" (xxiv) was sung by Gherardello (see Franco SACCHETTI, *Il libro delle Rime*, pp. 78-79). However, the musical setting was lost.

¹⁵ In the field of sacred music, only a two-voice *Gloria* and an *Agnus Dei* survive. However, we can also mention an *Ave*, *Credo* and *Osanna*, now all lost, cited in a sonnet by Simone Peruzzi (see F. SACCHETTI, *Il libro delle Rime*, pp. 175-176 and Gianluca D'AGOSTINO, "Gherardellus de Florentia", *Die Musik in Geschichte und Gegenwart Online*, Kassel, Bärenreiter, 2016).

¹⁶ Critical editions of Gherardello's madrigals are forthcoming and will be available online by 2025 on <https://www.europeanarsnova.eu>. Given this situation, the references presented throughout this article will refer to the manuscript sources on which the critical editions are based. Meanwhile readers may wish to consult the editions prepared by Nino Pirrotta ("The Music of Fourteenth Century Italy", *Corpus Mensurabilis Musicae*, 8-1, Amsterdam, American Institute of Musicology, 1954, pp. 53-80) or W. Thomas Marrocco ("Italian Secular Music", *Polyphonic Music of the Fourteenth Century*, vol. VII, Monaco, Éditions de l'Oiseau-lyre, 1971, pp. 75-119).

# ¹⁷	Madrigals	Musical/Textual Sources ¹⁸
1	<i>Allo spirar dell'arie brun m'aparve</i>	Sq f. 28r
2	<i>Cacciand' un giorn' alla vaga foresta</i>	Sq f. 29v
3	<i>Con levrieri e mastin, segugi e bracchi</i>	Fp ff. 84v-85r Lo f. 70v-71r Sq f. 27v
4	<i>Intrando ad abitar per una selva</i>	Fp f. 85v; Pit f. 27v-28r; Sq f. 31r
5	<i>La bella et la veççosa cavriola</i>	Sq f. 27v
6	<i>L'aquila bella, negra, pellegrina</i>	Sq f. 30r
7	<i>Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella</i>	Fp ff. 87v-88r; Sq f. 30v Mar f. 54r (text)
8	<i>Sì forte vola la pernice bella</i>	Sq f. 26r
9	<i>Sotto verdi fraschetti, molti augelli</i>	Sq f. 26v Fp ff. 88v-89r Lo f. 44v Pit ff. 26v-27r
10	<i>Una colonba più che neve bianca</i>	Sq ff. 28v-29r

Table 1: Gherardello da Firenze's madrigals

From a poetic perspective, Gherardello's madrigals are characterized by subjects related to metaphorical love expressed in idyllic scenarios. Written exclusively in hendecasyllables (*terzine* and *ritornelli*), all the poetic texts in the madrigals are by unknown authors¹⁹. Regarding the musical settings, it is notable that most ritornelli are *durchkomponiert*, since only four (from madrigals 2, 4, 8, 10) have both lines written with the same music.

Tonal space mapping strategy

The organisation of the tonal space is understood here as the abstract nexus resulting from a given pitch set, observed in its synchronous and directional existence. From this perspective, the sounds that are somehow highlighted or emphasised in the

¹⁷ The madrigals are presented here in alphabetical order and all further mentions refer to this table.

¹⁸ Siglas: Sq (Firenze, Biblioteca Medicea-Laurenziana, Ms. Mediceo Palatino 87); Fp (Firenze, Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale, Ms Panciatichi 26); Lo (London, British Library, Add. MS 29987); Pit (Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, fonds italien 568); Mar (Firenze, Biblioteca Marucelliana C.155).

¹⁹ Or possibly written by Gherardello himself. As N. Sapegno asserts, secure authorship attribution of sung texts is an exception in trecento music (Natalino SAPEGNO, *Poeti minori del Trecento*, p. 493). As mentioned *infra* (fn. 14), "Di bella palla e di valor di petra", written by Sacchetti, is the only known exception, although the musical setting is now lost.

composition reveal important points or “anchors” that we could use to map a particular use of the tones²⁰. Thus, the first step in the proposed tonal space analysis consists in determining parameters by which the segmentation choices will be guided, i.e., how the structural caesuras will be established.

It is important to emphasize that the term “caesura” is understood here in a broader meaning. The term will be applied to distinguish sonorities that provide some kind of interruption of the sound flow from a structural perspective²¹. Therefore, for methodological purposes, we consider two main classes of caesuras (as mentioned earlier): those established by sustentation and those by a rest. To determine such points, we propose a brief set of parameters.

Regarding the caesuras by sustentation, we adopt the referenced held value as being equivalent or closer to a *brevis* (or *longa* in *Longanotation*²²), which represents the measure unit basis of the analysed repertoire, and usually corresponds to a complete measure in modern notation transcription²³. Although the present category encompasses any kind of sustained sonority, these are generally derived from directed progressions, as shown in example 1.

However, in certain situations, the imperfect consonance that precedes the arrival tone is sustained instead of being resolved. Based on the continuum nature of the discourse and the effect caused by a directed progression, we assume that the prolongation of the unstabilised sonority may give the arrival tone a “caesura status”. This condition is assumed only if the imperfect consonance occurs over a full *brevis* – or, at least, $2/3$ in perfect *tempus* – and when the progression of the voices proceeds from imperfect to perfect consonance by stepwise and contrary motion²⁴, as seen in example 2²⁵. In sum, in this particular situation, the stressed emphasis prioritises the harmonically directed progression rather than the sustained resolution.

²⁰ Essentially, this approach resembles that of Pelinski’s regarding the terms *Ruhepunkte* (“rest points”) and *Ruheklänge* (“sonorities of repose”), applied in the analyses of Machaut’s motets (Rámon PELINSKI, “Zusammenklang und Aufbau in den Motetten Machauts”, *Die Musikforschung*, 28 (1975), p. 64).

²¹ Therefore, making a figurative use and considered from a structural perspective of its Latin root meaning, *caedere* (“to cut”), particularly in the sense of “a formal break or stop” as commonly applied by Latin rhetoricians and grammarians to distinguish sentence members (“Caesura”, *Oxford English Dictionary Online*, Oxford, Oxford University Press).

²² On this subject, see Marco Gozzi, “La cosiddetta *Longanotation*: nuove prospettive sulla notazione italiana del Trecento”, *Musica Disciplina*, 49 (1995), pp. 121-150.

²³ Thus, it is reasonable to understand that an equivalent sonority sustentation could establish a sort of interruption (i.e., caesura) of the musical discourse.

²⁴ In certain cases, the caesura can be established even in movements that do not necessarily proceed in this theoretically ruled way. In these cases, other contextual elements should be taken into account.

²⁵ This parameter matches what S. Fuller describes as “prepared arrivals”. Based on S. Fuller’s assertion, the unsettled quality of imperfect consonance remains crucial in determining here if the arrival sonority is a caesura. In her words: “The prepared arrivals, in absorbing previous tension, produce local closure and at least temporary tonal focus, for the goal toward which they aim becomes a promissory point of reference” (Sarah FULLER, “On Sonority in Fourteenth-Century Polyphony”, *Journal of Music Theory*, 30/1 (1986), p. 56).

Occasionally, we can also observe directed progressions in which the tenor establishes harmony with the cantus at a different pitch than expected; a comparable situation can occur with the cantus instead. It should be noted that these particular cases are not considered as directed progressions; they actually are considered as caesuras based solely on their sustentation state²⁶, as shown in example 3 regarding the sixth *E-c*²⁷.

Otherwise, for the determination of the caesura by rest(s), as seen in example 4, the based value is equivalent to a *semibrevis* (or to a *brevis* in *Longanotation*), which represents what can be called the “reference pulse”, and usually corresponds to a crotchet (simple or dotted) in modern notation transcription²⁸. It is worth mentioning that the rests in example 4 are preceded by a directed progression, which is not a necessary element for this particular caesura class (although a common one in this particular situation).

The image shows a musical score for two staves in 3x4 time signature. The lyrics are: fu già mai sì bel - mi le - vò da - van - . A dashed oval highlights the final note 'van' on both staves, with an arrow pointing to it from above.

Example 1: “Intrando ad abitar per una selva”, ritornello (Fp, f. 85r)

²⁶ Like the previous one, this parameter also matches S Fuller’s concept. These sustained sonorities correspond to what she calls “holds”, which “freeze the music on a sound that is detached without notice from its surroundings and brings no specific local action to completion” (Sarah FULLER., “On Sonority in Fourteenth-Century Polyphony”, p. 56). In addition, she also subdivides them into two separate categories according to their directional tendencies, calling them: “stable or neutral holds”, which are “perfect or imperfect in type, with no particular inclination toward another group of pitches”, and those “doubly-imperfect or inflected in nature, that is unsettled and has directed tendency” (*ibid.*, p. 56).

²⁷ In accordance with the usage observed in texts from the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, the capital letters (A to G) are used to refer to the notes of the lower octave, the small letters (a to g) to those of the middle octave, and the double small letters (aa to ee) to those of the upper fifth.

²⁸ In short, a basic parameter applied to the transcription of the trecento repertoire in modern notation, which corresponds to the binary or ternary division of the measure’s unit basis. It can be variable due to the features of the Italian notation system(s) or its partly/full transcription (or modernization) into the French system. On the subject, see Michele EPIFANI, “Una prospettiva ecdotica per le notazione del trecento italiano”, *Musica e poesia nel trecento italiano*, Antonio CALVIA and Maria Sofia LANNUTTI (ed.), Firenze, Edizioni del Galluzzo, 2015, pp. 189-235.

C
Sì e for - te
l'a - le

T
Sì e for - te
l'a - le

Example 2: “Sì forte vola la pernice bella”, beginning (Sq, f. 26r).
As is typical of these situations, the example has an elaborate ornamentation
in the cantus before the resolution

C
- - - - -

T
- - - - -

Example 3: “Con levrieri e mastin, segugi e bracchi”, third (sixth, ninth)
line (Fp, ff. 84v-85r)

C
sì
sso

T
sì
sso

Example 4: “Una colonba più che neve bianca”, ritornello (Sq, ff. 28v-29r)

Dealing with ambiguous cases

Despite the parameters, certain cases can be particularly ambiguous. Even in these circumstances, the caesuras will be established by their proximity to the two aforementioned classes, although some interpretation will be required.

One of those situations occurs in a passage of “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella” (example 5). Despite some doubts arising from the three highlighted progressions, all of them are considered as being neutral ones (or just part of the contrapuntal flow) according to the established criteria. This means that despite the imperfect-perfect consonance movements, at least one factor does not meet the criteria.

Preceding the first mark (*G-g*), the two repetitions of the major sixth *A-f#*, a consequence of the textual underlay, results in a structural “prolongation” rather than a “sustentation” in the strict sense²⁹. In the second mark, despite the concluding status of a melodic contour in both voices – which actually emphasises the beginning of the second hemistich –, the perfect consonance (*D-a*) is not considered a caesura due to the lack of sustentation for this specific consonance. Regarding the third and last mark, although both the previous *D* and *f#* are sustained, the resolution is highly attenuated by the fact that it does not occur on a perfect consonance, but an imperfect one instead, emerging as a sort of “evaded” tenor on *E* (rather on *C*)³⁰.

²⁹ Although they are related phenomena, they represent different forces in the discourse, where sustentation has a more articulating effect.

³⁰ It is worth noting that the technique of *finger di far cadentia* as such was conceptualized and theorized during the 16th century. Its use is also justified by other factors, such as its adherence to textual comprehensibility and the conclusion by at least one of the voices involved (mainly the tenor, in this context). One of the earliest known documented mentions of this concept stands out as set out by Giovanni Del Lago in his *Epistole composte in lingua volgare* (Ms. Vat.Lat. 5318, datable between 1535-1542). The evaded cadence technique is mentioned in a letter addressed to Fra Seraphin (dated 26 August 1541), particularly during Del Lago's explanation regarding the compositional use of the *soprano* voice. After some advice on the proper use of *soprano*'s range, he affirms: “[...] quando diminuirete le notule, farete il contrapunto con bella diminutione et sincope. Spesse volte fugare il soprano hor con il tenore, hor con il basso, o con altra parte. Alcuna volta *finger di far cadentia*, et poi nella conclusione di essa cadentia pigliare una consonantia non propinqua ad essa cadentia per accommodarsi e cosa laudabile, et questo se intende con il soprano o altra parte, ma bisogna che sempre il tenore in questo caso faccia egli la cadentia o ver distinctione, accio che sia intesa la sententia delle parole cantate.” (Boonie J. BLACKBURN, Edward E. LOWINSKY and Clement A. MILLER, *A Correspondence of Renaissance Musicians*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1991, p. 878, emphasis by the present author); English translation: “When you use short note-values, vary the counterpoint with ornaments and syncopations. Let the *soprano* frequently imitate the tenor, bass, or another part. Occasionally, it is advisable to pretend to cadence but end deceptively on a more distant degree in the *soprano* or another voice; the tenor, however, must cadence so that the meaning of the text may be understood.” (*Ibid.*, pp. 888-889).

fug - gi - mi cer - via stan - ca d' al - trui
 del don ch' a - vea_[c] più d' al - tro ca - ro_e
 ri - ma - se bian - co_e io di lei gio -

fug - gim - mi cer - via stan - ca d' al - trui
 del don ch' a - vea_[c] più d' al - tro ca - ro_e
 ri - ma - se bian - co_e io di lei gio -

Example 5: “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”,
 third (sixth, ninth) line (Fp, ff. 87v-88r)

Another similar situation is observed at the beginning of “Sotto verdi fraschetti, molti augelli” (example 6). Here three progressions occur in the initial melisma during the first and second syllables – which is typical of Gherardello’s style. As in the previous case, it is also necessary to examine the circumstantial details to see if they establish an articulation of the discourse according to the parameters.

The ambiguity arises mainly from the first two marks. While the second is characterised by a very attenuated directed progression (by means of the cantus ornamentation), the first seems to fit our criteria adequately. In this case, we must consider the context to be accurate.

As is typical, the madrigal begins with the voices a fifth apart; the tenor moves in steps first to the sixth, then to the octave (*F-f*) at the third measure. However, this imperfect consonance is greatly softened by the sonority that precedes it. In addition, it is important to realize that this takes place at the very beginning, which means that in the first line, the passage occurs without any previous harmonic activity; this situation is somewhat similar even in the second and the third *terzina*, when this imperfect consonance is necessarily preceded by two perfect consonances in a row: at the *terzina*’s conclusion – a unison (*a*) – and at the madrigal’s beginning – a fifth (*A-e*). From the present perspective, therefore, it seems that the major sixth in the second measure is understood more as a passage between perfect consonances (whether before or after the repetition of the *terzina*). A melodic sequence is then introduced in the cantus, leading to a caesura in the seventh measure, as indicated in the example 6.

Example 6: “Sotto verdi frascchetti, molti augelli”,
beginning (Sq, f. 26v)

Example 7 (“Allo spirar dell’arie”) also has a passage with some ambiguity concerning the task of distinguishing caesuras. Although the first arrow highlights a progression between an imperfect and a perfect consonance, it is not considered a caesura due to the lack of sound support (either the resolution or the preceding imperfect consonance); hence, there is no articulation of the discourse according to our guidelines. On the other hand, the second arrow indicates the caesura on the *G-d* sustained sonority, preceded by a sixth: in this case, we assume a directed progression due to the resolution of the cantus, despite the unexpected tenor leap towards the perfect consonance³¹. At the third and fourth arrows, the sustentation appears in the sonority before the resolution. Thus, based on the directional quality of the major sixth (*G-e*), we assume a caesura at its resolution (*F-f*).

Example 7: “Allo spirar dell’arie”, second (fifth, eighth) line (Sq f. 28r)

In general, ambiguous situations do not occur in caesuras by rests, since those shorter than a *semibrevis* are usually presented only as part of the contrapuntal flow (example 8) or as part of short *hoquetus* sections (example 9). In other situations, as in example 10, it

³¹ Thus, privileging the state of imperfect and perfect progression in general.

can be seen that sometimes only the cantus ceases after the sustentation while the tenor remains continuous. This particular feature, motivated either by physiological needs (usually in preparation for another melismatic passage) or by a stylistic trace – or even both –, additionally reinforces the next pitch attack due to the momentary absence of sound, and inevitably leads to a rhythmic variety on such stationary tenor sections.

Example 8: “La bella e la veççosa cavirola”, ending (Sq, f. 27r)

Example 9: “Sotto verdi fraschetti”, ritornello (Sq f. 26v)

Example 10: “Una colonba più che neve bianca”, second (fifth) line (Sq ff. 28v-29r)

Mapping the caesuras

The process of identifying internal caesuras starts with the initial and final sonorities of each poetic line. Since these points represent definite alignments between the music and the text where cyclical structure units begin and end, we might assume

that they are caesuras *par excellence*³². In this way, the madrigals will be evaluated by considering each line primarily as a distinctive and minimally complete *syntagma*³³. Then, each line will be evaluated from the perspective of the whole madrigal.

In order to manage the considerable amount of information collected, all the caesuras are condensed into a graph. Hence, the graph illustrates the caesuras that correspond to the metric position of the poetic text, as well as the pitch correspondence between the highlighted tones. In sum, the graph will provide a synthetic relationship between musical caesuras, directionality, and the poetic text.

As a very brief example of the procedure, the first line of “Per prender cacciagion lezzandra e bella” is used here to demonstrate how it works (example 11). Therefore, it is first necessary to establish all caesuras according to the previous guidelines, and then to set them up separately (as shown in example 12). The letter “p” and the number placed above the notes indicate the metrical position of the text that is inherent to each caesura. The caesuras are also distinguished by whether they are particularly based on the sustentation of the imperfect consonance that precedes their resolution (marked with a bracket), or on a neutral sonority (marked with an asterisk).

Secondly, for the sake of directionality, the pitch reiterations during the poetic line are highlighted and identified by a dotted slur. When the correspondence occurs specifically with the final sonority, then a regular slur is used (example 13). In the analysis, seven caesuras are distinguished: two that we could call “external” (in relation to the beginning and the end of the line) and five “internal”, with three of them on p10. Even though the majority of the caesuras are established as a consequence of directed progressions, the second arises from maintaining an imperfect consonance; similarly, the fifth and sixth caesuras are the result of sustained perfect consonances instead.

Regarding the question of ambiguity, the third caesura may be considered as being the most unclear. As part of a passage with four parallel fifths at the beginning of measures 6 to 9 (*D-a, F-c, G-d, a-e*), this sonority could be interpreted as merely a transitory sonority in the progression of fifths. But, as a *brevis*³⁴ held sonority, it has been established as a caesura based on the aforementioned criteria.

Thirdly, with brackets placed above the poetic metrical positions, we will identify the presence of what has been called “opening” or “closing” melismatic progressions – that is, the melismatic sections commonly observed at the beginning and end of the lines in these madrigals (example 14). If the second metrical position (p2) does not close the melismatic session, an open bracket should be used; the same applies when the final melisma begins at a different point than the tenth position (p10).

³² However, in other later Italian Ars Nova madrigals (such as those by Paolo da Firenze, for example), this view can be challenged, since some lines start and end without the support of a sustained sonority as occurs in Gherardello's madrigals.

³³ We use the term here analogously to its linguistic meaning, which is defined as “a set of linguistic forms in a sequential relationship” or “a string of syntactically related words”, i.e., a syntactical unit (“Syntagm”, *Oxford English Dictionary Online*, Oxford, Oxford University Press).

³⁴ In the original notation.

C

Per
Po
A

pre
chi
me

T

Per
Po
A

pre
chi
me

6

der cac - cia - gion lez - za - dra_e
se - gu - gi_a - ve - a_e po - chi
l'a - col - si - di - si - o - sa -

der cac - cia - gion lez - za - dra_e
se - gu - gi_a - ve - a_e po - chi
l'a - col - si - di - si - o - sa -

11

bel
vel
men

bel
vel
men

16

bel
vel
men

bel
vel
men

Example 11: “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella” (Fp ff. 87v-88r), first line of all three terzine. The transcription retained the figures at the ratio of 1:4 from the original notation (i.e., *brevis* = minim)

Example 12: “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”, first step in laying out the graph. The parenthesis concerns the caesura created by the sustentation of the imperfect consonance before its resolution. The asterisk concerns the caesura established by a sustained neutral sonority

Example 13: “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”, second step

Example 14: “Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”, third step

In the presentation of the sigla, the sonorities are always considered first by the cantus, given its apparent harmonic precedence³⁵. Considering that all the madrigals have two voices, the intervallic difference between the cantus and the tenor is added as a subscript number – a solution already adopted by M. Mangani and D. Sabaino³⁶ – with the inherent pitch according to the Guidonian system³⁷. In this case, the sequence of sonorities presented in the chart could be noted as: $a_1, d_8, c_5, e_5, c\#_6, a_1$ and d_8 .

Through this analysis, we have observed four internal caesuras in addition to the initial and final sonorities: d_8 (which coincides with the conclusion of the initial melisma, or p2), c_5, e_5 , the sixth between E and $c\#$ (which is a held sonority), and a_1 . It can also be seen that two pitches in each voice are correspondents: a - a , identified by a dotted slur, and the D - d , emphasised with a regular slur due to the relationship with the final sonority.

Similar structures are found in the other lines. In addition, there are correspondences between the first and last pitches of the tenor in the lines, except in the second, where it occurs only in the opening melismatic progression. Thus, in general, in the first line we have caesuras in $a_1, d_8, e_5, c\#_6, a_1$ and d_1 ; in the second, in aa_5, d_1, c_1, e_5 and b_1 ; and in the third, in e_5, g_8, a_1, d_8 and a_1 ; in the first line of the ritornello, caesuras are observed in aa_{12} and d_1 , and in the second, in e_5, d_8, d_8 and a_1 , as shown in example 15.

The image shows two musical staves, C (Cantus) and T (Tenor), with various intervals and caesuras marked below. The first staff is divided into three sections with intervals p1, p2, p4, p10, p11, p1, p10, p11, p1, p8, p10..., and p11. The second staff is divided into two sections with intervals p1, p11, p1, p10..., and p11.

Example 15: Chart of all lines (terzina and ritornello) of
“Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”

³⁵ As stated by Plumley regarding the French repertoire: “[...] there is considerable evidence that in the *Ars nova* chanson the cantus may have had compositional precedence, or at least represented the structural voice guiding the contrapuntal dimension” (Yolanda PLUMLEY, *The Grammar of 14th Century Melody*, p. 8). Regarding the Italian counterpart, in addition to Michael Long’s studies (“Landini’s Musical Patrimony: A Reassessment of Some Compositional Conventions in Trecento Polyphony,” *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, 40/1 (1987), pp. 31-52), the cantus-prior-status is also adopted and commented on by M. Mangani and D. Sabaino in their analysis of Nicolò’s repertoire (“L’organizzazione dello spazio sonoro”, pp. 255-256).

³⁶ Marco MANGANI and Daniele SABAINO, “L’organizzazione dello spazio sonoro”, pp. 261-280.

³⁷ Where the pitches are distinguished in *graves* (A, B, C...), *acutae* (a, b, c...), and *superacutae* (aa, bb, cc...), see note 27.

Analytical observations from the charts of all the madrigals

If we compare the charts of all Gherardello's madrigals, starting with those that conclude in "a" (example 16A), different pitch correspondences can be seen. Those madrigals which repeat the same music to both lines of the ritornello curiously present a greater number of pitch correspondences – and could then perhaps be considered to be more "stable sections" from a traditional tonal point of view. In this perception, "Una colomba più che neve bianca" may represent an exceptional and isolated case of traditional "tonal coherence" in Gherardello's repertoire, and may be almost related to mode 1, with the terminal sonority on *confinalis* (besides the *terzina*'s conclusion in c_1).

Regarding the other madrigals with finals in *c* and *d* (example 16B), different levels of correspondence can also be seen. Despite the presence of some similarities, such as the sonorities at the beginning of each line of the *terzina* in "Allo spiriar del'aire" and "La bella e la veççoça cavriola" – as well as the conclusion of their entire *terzine* sections – we could affirm, therefore, that these pieces do not appear to use the tonal space systematically.

Concerning the relationship between the range of the voices and the initial and final sonority of the lines, some particular observations can be made. For example, it is noteworthy that all the lines begin with the *cantus* at a pitch equal to or higher than the previous one. The only exception to this can be found between the second and third lines of "Sì forte vola la pernice bella". This habit seems to reinforce certain aspects of the musical setting, underlining both the poetic structure and the formal musical units.

These charts also show the recurring tenor repetition between the end and the immediate beginning of the next line. In addition, it should be noted that the melodic lines are usually based on the species *re-la* and *re-sol* (in terms of solmisation) but applied indifferently from the *finalis* or the ambitus. Likewise, a notorious polarization in *a* is observed – even though some madrigals conclude in *c* (1, 5 and 6), or *d* (8 and 9). The *cantus*, on the other hand, does not show any predominance of any species, although the diapente *re-la* is slightly more frequent.

An almost immediate question regarding these charts is whether there is a correlation between such caesuras and the ambitus of the voices in these madrigals. This needs to be checked to determine the extent of their association.

An initial survey of their ambitus shows that they are remarkably similar (example 17), and in some cases, even identical. The tenor's range is typically around *D-d* or *C-c* (except in madrigals 2, 4, and 5), while the *cantus*' range is around *a-aa* or *G-g* (except in madrigals 8 and 4).

7 *Per prender cacciagion*

8 *Con leonin e masin*

9 *Cacciand' un giorn'*

10 *Intrando ad abitar*

11 *Una columba*

Example 16A: Charts of Gherardello's madrigals with a terminal sonority in 'a'

1 *Alta spina dell'aire*

2 *La bella et la visposa*

3 *L'agnola bella*

4 *Si forte vola*

5 *Sotto vanti franchetti*

Example 16B: Charts of Gherardello's madrigals with a terminal sonority in 'c' and 'd'

Regarding the tenor, the ambitus of the madrigals, as shown in the upper row in example 17, could be associated with a particular octave species. Despite the differences in the final sonorities of the *terzina* or the *ritornello* (which are presented after the number of madrigals in the example), it is worth noting that madrigals 7, 1, 10, and 8 have the same ambitus as the tenor (*C-d*). Madrigals 9 and 6, with ranges between *D-d*, differ from madrigal 2, whose ambitus is *C-c*. In the bottom row, the remaining madrigals (3, 4 and 5) all have tenors with expanded ranges, with only one similar to the cantus (madrigal 4).

The cantus also displays a degree of homogeneity in its ambitus. This can be seen in the common range of the madrigals 7 and 1, as well as in the madrigals 10, 3, and 5.³⁸

Except for madrigal 4, the average distance between the voices is approximately a fifth, which can generally be considered the result of an ordinary arrangement between the voices to achieve better individual ranges of action in contrapuntal terms³⁹.

7 (a_1/a_4) 1 (a_1/a_4) 10 (c_1/a_4) 8 (a_1/a_4) 9 (a_1/a_4) 6 (d_1/a_4) 2 (a_1/a_4)

C
6 6 6 6 5 6 3 7 5 5 3 5 3 7

T

3 (a_1/a_4) 4 (a_1/a_4) 5 (a_1/a_4)

4 4 1 3 5 2

Example 17: Voice ranges of the madrigals with their intervals between extremes. The sonorities indicated after each madrigal number refer to both the final sonorities of the *terzina* and the *ritornello*. The placement is based on the similarity of the tenor's range

Therefore, when comparing the two elements, it is clear that there is no systematic relationship between the ambitus of the voices and the final sonorities⁴⁰. To provide a brief comparison of equivalent vocal ranges, the following graph (example 18) shows three madrigals with similar ambitus. Two of them even have identical voice pairs, albeit with different conclusive sonorities.

³⁸ Moreover, it is not necessary that the permanence around *G-bb* is in any way related to performance convenience.

³⁹ According to Dorothea Baumann, this finding can be applied to other two-voice madrigals and ballads throughout the Italian *Ars Nova*. D. Baumann mentions that, in addition to the fifth, the fourth is also a commonly observed distance between the two voices. (See Dorothea BAUMANN, *Die Dreistimmige Italienische Lied-Satztechnik im Trecento*, Baden-Baden, Valentin Koerner, 1979, p. 25).

⁴⁰ For a more in-depth analysis – reserved for further studies – it would be necessary to compare the internal caesuras in order to obtain more precise indications for a view on the features of the use of tonal space, by considering their respective vocal extensions (and comparing them).

The image displays three musical score examples, labeled 7, 1, and 9, each consisting of two staves (C and T). The scores are annotated with various musical notations and labels:

- Example 7:** Features dynamic markings p1, p2, p4, p8, p10, p11, and p12. Interval labels include d1, d5, and d12. A bracket labeled e5 spans the final two staves.
- Example 1:** Features dynamic markings p1, p2, p4, p8, p10, p11, and p12. Interval labels include d1, d5, and d8. A bracket labeled e5 spans the final two staves.
- Example 9:** Features dynamic markings p1, p2, p4, p10, p11, and p12. Interval labels include d1, d5, and d8. A bracket labeled e5 spans the final two staves.

Example 18: Comparison between vocal ranges and caesuras between madrigals 7 (“Per prender cacciagion leççadra e bella”), 1 (“Allo spirar dell’arie brun m’aparve”) and 9 (“Sotto verdi fraschetti, molti augelli”)

A certain similarity can be seen in external caesuras, specifically in madrigals 1 and 9; the same is true for the terminal sonority of the *terzina* (which is also associated with madrigal 7). However, each ritornello is articulated differently: they do not share the initial and final melismatic progressions, nor the positioning of the caesuras according to the metric positions of the poetic text. In addition, each madrigal has a different terminal sonority, although they share the same *terzina* endings.

From a directionality perspective, however, the notes *a* and *d* predominate in the caesuras, regardless of the terminal sonority. Furthermore, the last *terzina* corresponds to the concluding sonority (*a*) in all three madrigals without distinction. In general, the preference for *a* in the conclusion of the *terzina* is seen in eight out of ten madrigals (except for 10 and 6). This limits the number of choices for the initial sonorities to a contrapuntally compatible ritornelli: e_5 (4, 10, 1, 6); aa_{12} (madrigals 7, 8); and aa_5 (3, 5⁴¹, 9), with a prevalence of a leap in the cantus, while the tenor remains on the same pitch between the sections.

Moreover, it should be pointed out that all the madrigals whose ritornello begins on e_5 (which is the majority, as highlighted) have the second line ending in d_1 (madrigals 4 and 10) or d_8 (1 and 6), with terminal sonorities on a_1 and a_8 , respectively. Although this relationship exists, it is not systematically established from the perspective of the conclusion of the second line, since madrigals 2 and 9 also end that line in d_8 but have the beginning of the ritornello on aa_8 and aa_5 , respectively, with a terminal sonority on a_1 and d_1 .

This evidence shows that directionality in Gherardello's madrigals is more systematically treated in the last line of the *terzina* (even considering the two aforementioned exceptions). However, it cannot be claimed that a polarisation in *a* (or *re-la* in terms of solmisation) indicates a systematic treatment of the tonal space of the entire madrigal.

Towards a statistical output of the caesuras

To reinforce and expand on the previous findings from the chart analysis, it is also possible to present the map of caesuras using statistical output. To achieve this, the data must be converted into a concise alphanumeric form, allowing for tabulation and better comparison⁴².

For our purposes, table 1 highlights the caesuras of the previous charts and includes some additional information, such as the system signature in each voice, the range of the voices, the initial sonorities, the caesuras observed up to the p10 syllable, those along with the p10; and the final sonority of the line.

⁴¹ In fact, as only the cantus is presented, the ritornello begins with aa_0 . The first caesura occurs after the tenor's entrance, establishing the sonority aa_5 considered here.

⁴² M. Mangani and D. Sabaino have already presented a similar codification ("L'organizzazione dello spazio sonoro", pp. 261-280).

Madrigal	Sign.	Amb.	V.	Initial sonority	Caesuras (until p10)	Caesuras (during p10)	Final sonority
7	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>a-bb</i> T: <i>C-d</i>	1	a_1	$(d_8; *c_5)$	$e_5; *c_6; a_1$	d_8
			2	aa_5	d_1	$c_1; e_5$	b_1
			3	e_5	(g_{10})	$a_1; d_8$	a_1
			R1	aa_{12}	-	-	d_1
			R2	e_5	-	$d_8; (d_8)$	a_1
3	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>G-bb</i> T: <i>D-f</i>	1	e_5	$d_1; d_8; g_5$	g_8	a_1
			2	g_8	$(g_8); d_1$	d_8	G_1
			3	e_5	$*c_6$	$d_1; *c_6; e_5$	a_1
			R1	a_5	-	-	$*c_6$
			R2	e_5	d_8	a_1	a_1
2	C: ♭ T: ♯	C: <i>E-bb</i> T: <i>C-c</i>	1	d_5	G_1	$d_8; a_5$	E_1
			2	e_8	$d_8; (G_1)$	c_8	d_8
			3	aa_{12}	$d_5; d_8; a_1$	$d_8; d_5$	a_1
			R1	aa_8	$(g_8); *d_5$	$d_8; a_1; *c[\sharp]_6$	a_1
			{R2} ⁴³	aa_8	$(g_8); *d_5$	$d_8; a_1; *c[\sharp]_6$	a_1
4	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>C-aa</i> T: <i>C-f</i>	1	c_0	-	$c_5; (c_8); (c_8)^{44}$	G_1
			2	e_5	$d_1; g_8$	e_5	d_1
			3	e_5	$d_8; a_1$	$d_8; a_1; (g_8); (d_8)$	a_1
			R1	e_5	$(g_8); d_8$	$g_8; g_8; (aa_{12}); d_8$	a_1
			{R2}	e_5	$(g_8); d_8$	$g_8; g_8; (aa_{12}); d_8$	a_1
10	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>G-bb</i> T: <i>C-d</i>	1	d_8	$G_1; d_5$	$d_8; *e_{10}; d_5$	d_8
			2	aa_{12}	d_5	$*e_5; d_5; aa_{12}; *d_5; *e_5$	d_1
			3	aa_5	$(g_8); d_8$	$d_1; d_1; e_5$	c_1
			R1	e_5	$(g_8); d_8; *e_5$	$g_8; aa_{12}; e_8$	a_1
			{R2}	e_5	$(g_8); d_8; *e_5$	$g_8; aa_{12}; e_8$	a_1
1	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>G-aa</i> T: <i>C-d</i>	1	d_5	d_5	$a_5; *c_6; a_1$	d_8
			2	e_5	$*e_5$	$d_5; *e_{10}; *d_5; (f_8)$	d_8
			3	aa_{12}	e_5	$d_5; a_1$	a_1
			R1	e_5	$*e_6$	-	a_1
			R2	e_5	-	$(d_5); (f_8)$	c_1
5	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>G-bb</i> T: <i>C-aa</i>	1	d_5	$(d_8); c_8$	$G_1; e_5; *d_5; e_{10}$	b_5
			2	e_5	-	$e_5; *e_5; d_8; *e_5; c[\sharp]_3$	$*c[\sharp]_6$
			3	aa_{12}	-	$a_1; d_8; e_5$	a_1
			R1	aa_0	$aa_5; e_5$	-	d_1
			R2	aa_{12}	$*c_6$	-	c_1
6	C: ♭ T: ♯	C: <i>F♯-aa</i> T: <i>D-d</i>	1	d_5	$(d_8); G_1$	a_5	a_1
			2	g_5	$d_5; c_1$	e_5	d_8
			3	d_1	$d_1; *d_5$	$*e_5$	d_1
			R1	e_5	a_1	-	$*c[\sharp]_6$
			R2	g_8	$*d_5$	$*e_5$	c_1
8	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>E-cc</i> T: <i>C-d</i>	1	a_5	(d_8)	$*c_6; a_5$	E_1
			2	e_5	a_5	$(g_8); d_1$	f_8
			3	aa_5	$aa_8; *f_{10}$	$(aa_{12}); *e_{10}$	a_1
			R1	aa_{12}	d_1	$aa_8; g_8$	d_1
			{R2}	aa_{12}	d_1	$a_8; g_8$	d_1
9	C: ♯ T: ♯	C: <i>a-aa</i> T: <i>D-d</i>	1	e_5	a_1	$*b_5$	a_1
			2	g_8	a_1	-	d_8
			3	e_5	$d_1; d_5$	$a_1; g_8$	a_1
			R1	aa_5	-	-	$*c_6$
			R2	f_6	-	-	d_1

Table 1: Tabulated caesuras from examples 16A and 16B

⁴³ Curly brackets identify the repetition of music in the second line of the ritornello.⁴⁴ p10 regarding the tenor (see example 16A).

Table 2 presents three groups of general comparative factors concerning the external caesuras of the madrigals. The data are distributed as follows: (1) sonorities that conclude the madrigal as well as the entire *terzina* section; (2) sonorities presented at the end of each line, whether from the *terzina* or the *ritornelli*; and (3) sonorities that start the madrigal, as well as each of the *terzina* and *ritornelli* lines.

It is noteworthy that a_1 is prevalent in 80% of conclusive sessions in *terzina* cases. This confirms the observation previously made about the prominence of such sonorities. Regarding the data from the beginning of the lines, the prevalence of e_5 was observed in both sections, with a higher incidence in the lines of the *ritornelli* (45%).

Thus, although the relationship between e_5 and a_1 suggests the alignment with the species of the fifth *re-la*, it is not supported by internal caesuras.

	Factor	Sonority	% (total)
1)	Final sonority of the madrigal	a_1	70
		c_1	30
		d_1	10
	Conclusive sonority of the <i>terzina</i>	a_1	80
		c_1	10
		d_1	10
2)	Conclusive sonority of the lines of the <i>terzina</i>	a_1	36,6
		d_8	23,3
		d_1	10
		E_1	6,6
		G_1	6,6
		b_1	3,3
		b_5	3,3
		$c\#_6; f\#_3; c_1$	3,3 (each)
	Conclusive sonority of lines of the <i>ritornello</i>	a_1	45
		d_1	25
		c_1	15
		$c\#_6$	15

3)	Initial sonority of the madrigal	e_5	40
		d_5	30
		a_5	10
		a_1	10
		c_1	10
	Initial sonority of the lines of the terzina	e_5	33
		e_8	3,3
		aa_{12}	13,3
		aa_5	10
		a_5	3,3
		a_1	3,3
		d_5	13
		d_1	6,6
		G_1	6,6
		G_5	3,3
	c_0	3,3	
	Initial sonority of the lines of the ritornello	e_5	45
		a_5	30
		a_1	15
		g_8	5
$f\sharp_6$		5	

Table 2: Comparative statistics on external caesuras

Table 3 presents the correlation between the beginning and ending sonorities of each line, along with the percentage regarding the total number of cases. Despite the higher correlation between e_5 and a_1 (with 13 occurrences) – accounting for 68,4% of the cases associated with this particular beginning –, the data reveals that the relation between aa_{12} and d_1 (with 4 occurrences) is quite prominent.

Initial sonority of the line	Conclusive sonority of the line	Occurrences	% per initial sonority	% total of cases
d_1	E_1	1	50	2
	d_8	1	50	2
d_8	d_8	1	100	2
d_5	a_1	2	66,6	4
	b_5	1	33,3	2
e_5	a_1	13	68,4	26
	$c\#_6$	2	10,4	4
	d_8	1	5,2	2
	d_1	1	5,2	2
	c_1	1	5,2	2
	f_8	1	5,2	2
e_8	d_8	1	100	2
aa_{12}	d_1	4	50	8
	a_1	3	37,5	6
	c_1	2	12,5	4
aa_8	a_1	2	66,6	4
	aa_8	1	33,3	2
aa_5	a_1	1	100	2
aa_0	d_1	1	50	2
	$c\#_6$	1	50	2
a_5	$c\#_6$	2	40	4
	a_1	1	20	2
	c_1	1	20	2
	E_1	1	20	2
a_1	d_8	1	100	2
g_8	G_1	1	33,3	2
	c_1	1	33,3	2
	d_8	1	33,3	2
c_0	g_1	1	100	2
$f\#_6$	d_1	1	100	2

Table 3: Statistics on the relationship between the initial and final sonorities of the lines

In a brief comparison with Jacopo da Bologna's and Nicolò del Preposto's madrigals, the preference for a_1 or d_1 terminal sonorities is particularly noteworthy, as shown in table 4. Those concerning c_1 , however, are more evenly distributed, although Gherardello's madrigals have the highest percentage.

Composer	Final sonority of the madrigal	Occurrences	% (total)
Gherardello da Firenze	a_1	5	50
	c_1	3	30
	d_1	3	20
Nicolò del Preposto	d_1	9	60
	a_1	3	20
	c_1	3	20
Jacopo da Bologna	a_1	10	41,6
	d_1	7	29,1
	c_1	5	20,8
	e_1	1	4,1
	f_8	1	4,1

Table 4: Statistics of the final sonority of madrigals by Gherardello, Nicolò and Jacopo

We also verify the *re-la* alignment between the conclusion of the *terzine* and the final sonority of the madrigal: i.e., between the conclusion of the *terzina* in d_1 (or d_8)⁴⁵ or a_1 and the terminal sonorities of the madrigal. In Gherardello's madrigals, 5 out of 10 cases (50%) can be identified, in Nicolò's, 9 out of 17 ($\approx 53\%$), and in Jacopo's, 11 out of 24 madrigals ($\approx 45\%$). In other words, on average, 50% of the madrigals by these three composers exhibit the identified characteristics. Although this data is significant, the percentage alone remains insufficient to verify any systematic treatment.

* * *

⁴⁵ As in Jacopo's madrigals: "Entrava Febo con lucenti raggi", "I' mi son un che per le frase' andando", and "Posando sovr' un'acqua, in sogno vidi".

It should be noted that while vernacular poetry may imitate Latin poetic model in order to ascend as an art form⁴⁶, the organisation of tonal space in secular music does not necessarily follow the same path as the Latin *cantus* repertoire. Thus, the distinction is remarkable: music is *ars* through its fundamental elements, and not necessarily through its elaboration or formal ordering.

In the case of Gherardello's madrigals analysed here, the preliminary conclusion is that, although there is some alignment in directionality – especially in the tenors –, it is not possible to determine whether they establish a system from a perspective of tonal space.

Based on the similarities between vocal ranges and caesuras, such points of articulation do not seem to be influenced by a prior systemic organisation or even oriented by a *finalis*. As the analytical charts show, the organisation of the tonal spaces seems to be based on a combination of contrapuntal variety and performance convenience, guided by the distinct ranges of action of the voices. From this perspective, each madrigal projects a unique chain of tonal relationships that promotes a particular nexus to the musical discourse.

Consequently, any reading based on the “minimal markers” – i.e., an analysis based solely on the system, the ambitus of the voices, and the *finalis* – will be incompatible with the tonal features found in these madrigals⁴⁷. Although the results might superficially show a predominance of certain fifth or fourth species, such a conclusion would not take into account the entire tonal complex of the piece. Instead, its results would be based only on a general predominance of similar action zones.

Therefore, despite the polarisation around *a*, the evidence presented here reinforces M. Mangani and D. Sabaino's conclusions about Nicolò del Preposto: the treatment of tonal space in Gherardello's madrigals does not develop in a way that could establish a system.

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⁴⁶ See Dante ALIGHIERI, *De vulgari eloquentia*, II, IV, 3, p. 290: “quantum illos proximius imitemur, tantum rectius poetemur” (Dante ALIGHIERI, *De vulgari eloquentia*, 1996, p. 57: “the more closely we try to imitate the great poets, the more correctly we write poetry”).

⁴⁷ On the issue that is particularly related to the Italian Ars Nova repertoire, see Marco MANGANI and Daniele SABAINO, “L'organizzazione dello spazio sonoro”, pp. 239-240.

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RÉSUMÉS

Carlos IAFELICE, Approche analytique de l'organisation de l'espace tonal des madrigaux de Gherardello

Cette étude propose une approche analytique pour cartographier l'organisation de l'espace tonal dans les madrigaux du compositeur italien du Trecento, Gherardello da Firenze. La méthode se concentre sur le processus de segmentation, spécifiquement appliqué à la relation entre les « césures » musicales et leurs interactions respectives avec la structure poétique. Le mécanisme analytique est appliqué à chaque verset pris isolément, en les condensant en graphiques. Les résultats sont également présentés sous forme de résultats statistiques, permettant des comparaisons plus directes avec d'autres compositeurs du cercle de Gherardello.

Mots clés : Gherardello da Firenze, madrigal du XIV^e siècle, modalité, organisation de l'espace tonal

Nicolas MEEÛS, Qu'est-ce qu'un savart ?

Alors que l'histoire des logarithmes musicaux est relativement bien connue, la nature exacte du savart demeure incertaine. Les sources ne s'accordent pas sur son origine : certaines, mais pas toutes, en attribuent la paternité à Félix Savart (1791-1841) lui-même ; aucune apparemment n'a noté sa parenté avec les heptamérides de Sauveur ; enfin, il ne semble jamais y avoir eu consensus sur une valeur normalisée du savart. L'article s'efforcera de mettre un peu d'ordre dans cette histoire. Il tentera d'expliquer cette « exception française » et de réhabiliter le nom de l'inventeur du savart, Auguste Guillemin (1842-1914), pratiquement oublié aujourd'hui. Il montrera que la valeur du savart, le logarithme décimal de 2 multiplié par 1000, parce qu'elle est un nombre irrationnel, n'a jamais été normalisée. Le savart a toujours été relativement facile à calculer, mais le résultat du calcul est toujours demeuré relativement imprécis.

Mots clés : Félix Savart, logarithmes musicaux, Auguste Guillemin, heptaméride

ABSTRACTS

Carlos IAFELICE, An analytical approach to the organisation of tonal space in Gherardello's madrigals

This study proposes an analytical approach to mapping the organisation of the tonal space in the madrigals of the early Italian Trecento composer, Gherardello da Firenze. The method focuses on the process of segmentation, specifically applied to the relationship between the musical "caesuras" and their respective interactions with the poetic structure. The analytical mechanism is applied individually to each verse, condensing them into graphical charts. The results are also presented in statistical form, allowing more direct comparisons with other composers in Gherardello's circle.

Keywords: Gherardello da Firenze, 14th-century madrigal, modalism, organisation of tonal space

Nicolas MEEÛS, What is a savart?

While the history of musical logarithms is relatively well known, the precise nature of the savart remains uncertain. The sources do not agree on its origin: some, but not all, attribute its authorship to Félix Savart (1791-1841) himself; none apparently have noted the kinship with Sauveur's heptameride; and there does not seem to ever have been a consensus on a standardised value of the savart. The article will try to put some order into this matter. It will attempt to explain this "French exception" and rehabilitate the name of the inventor of the savart, Auguste Guillemin (1842-1914), who is virtually forgotten today. It will show that the value of the savart, 1000 times the decimal logarithm of 2, because it is an irrational number, has never been standardised. The savart has always been relatively easy to compute, but the result of the computation has always remained rather imprecise.

Keywords: Félix Savart, musical logarithms, Auguste Guillemin, heptameride